

**POETICS OF SOCIAL CHRONOTOPE IN "REBELLION AND
OBEDIENCE" BY ULUGBEK HAMDAM AND "THE MOON AND
SIXPENCE" BY SOMERSET MOEM**

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ANNOTATION

In this thesis, the scientific research consists of studying the concepts of man and society in Uzbek and English literature, that is, in the works of Ulugbek Hamdam and Somerset Maugham, their comparative analysis and finding their uniqueness will be briefly covered. The scientific novelty of the research conducted on these works is that the similar and different aspects of the concept of interaction between man and society in Uzbek and English literature were carried out on the basis of a comparative analysis. In the works of writers, the specific characteristics of the ideas of "man and society", the causes and consequences of the problems in mutual relations, the influence of these complications on the human psyche, and the role of this work in the analysis of the artistic light have been studied.

Key words: human, society, character, reality, socio-psychological concepts, system, analysis, research.

It is clear to all of us that literature is the art of words, the expression of the people's heart, the herald of truth and justice. Due to our national independence, a number of updates are taking place in our literature, as in all fields. In addition to formal and substantive updates in the works of literary critics and artists, unique new views are also manifested in the views of the art of speech and creativity. "The literature of the period of independence is turning from the literature of problems, from the literature that raises actual issues, to the literature that artistically explores and examines the layers of the human psyche."

In the work of Ulugbek Hamdam and Somerset Maugham, the issue of man and society is covered in one or another aspect in our literature, but it has not been studied as a whole. The relevance of the scientific work is determined by the scientific-artistic approach to the issue of macro- and micro-chronotope, comparing only one example of the writers' creativity. The relevance of this scientific work is determined by this.

The relevance of the study is as follows:

- a) the need to deeply research the role of the concept of man and society in Uzbek and world literature and controversial theories;
- b) formation of relations between man and society and research of this idea;
- c) analysis of artistic interpretation as one of the elements determining the principles of forming relationships in the works of writers;
- d) consists of analyzing the artistic image of social factors that created macrochronotope and microchronotope in the works. Structural methods were mainly used in the research, with a comparative-typological and descriptive role. Research can be conditionally divided into three groups according to its nature and essence:
 - mutual relations between man and society;
 - analysis of images in works;
 - the combination of macrochronotopes and microchronotopes;

The tasks of the research are as follows: extensive research and analysis of the role of man in society in the artistic process, study of the direct and indirect effects of society on the psyche of the hero, study of the problem of the creative personality in the work "The Moon and Sixpence", clarification of its characteristics, "Rebellion and Obedience" the relationship between man and society in the works through the images of the master and student who create the conceptual idea of the novel "Rebellion and Obedience", researching updates in terms of the theme and the scope of images, showing the methods and means of creating images, characters and types of writers, macrochronotope and It consists of elucidating the metaphorical harmony of the microchronotope, researching the ideological-artistic intention and skill in creating symbolic images, based on the analysis, elucidating the traditions and peculiarities of the writer's style, developing general conclusions and recommendations on the topic. The artistic interpretation of the relationship between man and society in the works "Rebellion and Obedience" and "The Moon and Sixpence", the direct and indirect influence of the society on the psyche of the hero, the image, character and type in the work "Rebellion and Obedience", in the novel "The Moon and Sixpence" the problem of the creative personality, the analysis of the images of the teacher and the student creating the conceptual idea of the novel "Rebellion and Obedience". Writers' new views on the system of images and narrative style were clarified. In the works, reflecting a wide range of human psyche, thoughts, feelings in various conflicting colors, depicting the problems occupying the consciousness of mankind with all their complexity, striving to vividly reveal the high national and universal essence of the individual became the leading direction. In the novel "Rebellion and Obedience" the theme of man and his inner world is at the center of the theme. Man is portrayed as the

most beautiful creature and as helpless in front of fate no matter how hard he tries.

“Little by little white snow will fall.

Gardens are a divine garment.

“Isn't the meaning of being born and living in the world to feel this beauty, to pay attention to it?” Akbar used to reflect on the stork flying in front of his eyes and instantly melting away. enjoying the snow...”

“...Finally, love! Only now he is trying to teach me something, and I am also excited with my breath catching in my throat. The secret of the matter, I still do not know it better, but the greatest wisdom of life is held as in love. Rub and let it be, rub and don't be deceived. I can't bear it if my expectations turn out to be a mirage again. Despite the guilt, I will kill myself. However, he has already lost his sweetness...” The role of artistic psychologism in creating a microchronotop of an artistic hero cannot be denied, and each of its available methods increases the full understanding and effectiveness of the work. Also, the events are described by the inner experiences of the hero, his feelings, thoughts and judgments, and the dynamics of his thoughts. In this, one feeling gives rise to another feeling, one thought gives rise to another thought, they complement each other and change their quality. This form makes it possible to show sharp turns in the fate and thinking of the characters, which is why some researchers call it the form of "dialectic of the soul".

Akbar opened his eyelids, moved slowly and followed the large notebook lying open on the writing table and wrote: "A heart without rebellion will not obey." He added “Rebellion” next to the word “Obedience” written in letters. Akbar had been looking for this name for several years, but he didn't find it!... – “REBELLION and OBEDIENCE”, here it is - a very difficult way to become a human being, this is the fate written on the forehead of mankind...

In the novel “The Moon and Sixpence” through the dynamic principle, the psyche of the hero is expressed through his actions, facial expressions and gestures, his behavior in various life situations and his words, in essence, it is similar to the way of revealing the psyche of the characters of the dramatic work. therefore, the dynamic principle is sometimes described as the “dramaturgical method” of psychological analysis. “I tell you I've got to paint. I can't help myself. When a man falls into the water it doesn't matter how he swims, well or badly: he's got to get out or else he'll drown.”¹

“I paused, and I looked at him searchingly.

¹ Somerset M. The great novels and short stories of Somerset Maugham. Skyhorse and Skyhorse Publishing. 2014 – P. 191.

“What’s the good of trying to humbug me?” I said.

“I don’t know what you mean.”

I smiled.

“Let me tell you. I imagine that for months the matter never comes into your head, and you’re able to persuade yourself that you’ve finished with it for good and all. You rejoice in your freedom, and you feel that at last you can call your soul your own. You seem to walk with your head among the stars. And then, all of a sudden you can’t stand it anymore, and you notice that all the time your feet have been walking in the mud. And you want to roll yourself in it. And you find some woman coarse and low and vulgar, some beastly creature in whom all the horror of sex is blatant, and you fall upon her like a wild animal. You drink till you’re blind with rage.”² In the psychological image, the dynamics of the human mental life, mental states in the mental and spiritual mood are modeled. This spirit allows us to divide or find a way to the "real, almost unbelievable truth" of the inner world of the person and the "existing reality". With these tools, the writer can reflect the circumstances of the hero’s life in his picture. Therefore, it is not a mistake to think that the creation of a microchronotope of an image through artistic psychologism can come from the author's goal and style. Artistic psychologism generally interprets issues such as the essence of fiction, the general laws of literary development, its role and tasks in the life of society, the nature of a work of art and its structure, and reveals general laws on this basis. With its help, principles of analysis of works of art, evaluation criteria, analysis methods are developed. In conclusion, we can emphasize that in Uzbek and English literature, society has a special importance in illuminating people's lives and problems in society and finding solutions to them. With the help of these, we analyze not only one topic, but many news about the writing style of writers and their similarities. Writers' works on the topic and a more in-depth study of such works can be continued for future research. The two writers we tried to research also used many quotes from their nations and cultures to explain their ideas in their works. Uzbek and English writers raised the human factor to a higher level than ever before, and linked his artistic power, perception, potential, mental and spiritual perfection directly to technical development, technological development and civilization, and the surrounding society. describe the lips. The importance of fiction, including novels, in human life is very high. Humanity, justice, compassion, mutual

² Somerset M. The great novels and short stories of Somerset Maugham. Skyhorse and Skyhorse Publishing. 2014 – P. 216.

solidarity, friendship, love and immortal human feelings such as love are embodied in the mind, consciousness, and spirit of a person, and these feelings enter the hearts of people who are familiar with literature. will move. Emotions are felt and influenced not only through the mind, but also through the mind and heart. Therefore, the artistic interpretation of these events is an important and integral component of fiction. Man and his perfection, his search for his originality, concern for his spiritual perfection, controversial and problematic relations between man and society; problems of such loose connections, such as artistic image and the great role of artistic psychology in depicting the effects on humanity, became the main idea of the works of Ulugbek Hamdam and Somerset Maugham. As a result of our scientific research and comparative analysis of the works, we came to the conclusion that the works of these two writers have features proportional to each other. However, despite this, each of them has its own place in literature with its own artistic direction, the principle of creating the subject and the spirit of images.

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